

A validated RP-HPLC method for quantitative determination of sodium taurocholate in bovine bile extract

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Abstract

Sodium taurocholate, a major component of bile salts, plays an important role in pharmaceutical and biochemical applications. This study aimed to develop and validate a high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method for accurately determining sodium taurocholate in bovine bile extracts. Chromatographic separation was carried out using a Shodex C18-4E column (250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm), with a mobile phase composed of methanol and 25 mM phosphate buffer solution, pH 5.45, at a flow rate of 0.7 mL/min. The analytes were detected with a UV detector set at 210 nm. The method was validated for selectivity, linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantification (LOQ). The calibration curve showed linearity over the range of 10–100 μg/mL, with a correlation coefficient (*r*) of 0.9997. Intra-day and inter-day precision ranged from 0.60% to 1.28%. Spike recovery of sodium taurocholate ranged from 100.01% to 100.93%. The limit of detection and limit of quantification for sodium taurocholate were 2.83 μg/mL and 8.57 μg/mL, respectively. The validated method ensures reliable and reproducible quantification, making it suitable for quality control applications.

Keywords

Bile extract, bovine, HPLC method, method validation, pharmaceutical analysis, sodium taurocholate

Introduction

Dissolution testing is a critical tool in pharmaceutical development for assessing the *in vitro* performance of oral dosage forms, particularly in predicting their *in vivo* behavior. (De Lemos et al. 2022). Developing *in vitro–in vivo* correlation (IVIVC) can improve product quality and support compliance with regulatory requirements (Fotaki and Vertzoni 2010). Several factors can influence dissolution testing outcomes, including physicochemical

properties of the active pharmaceutical ingredient, such as solubility and particle size, excipient composition, medium pH, temperature, and agitation speed (Newton and Muhammad 1984; Sun et al. 2012).

The dissolution medium used in dissolution testing must reflect the physiological conditions of the human gastrointestinal tract to provide results relevant to biological responses. Biorelevant dissolution media are designed to resemble human digestive fluids, such as gastrointestinal fluids, which play a significant role in the dissolution and absorption of

drugs. Human digestive fluids contain bile acids, phospholipids, and electrolytes (Augustijns and Brewster 2007). Therefore, biorelevant dissolution media might provide a better prediction of the *in vivo* performance of drug products.

Sodium taurocholate (Fig. 1) is a bile salt that plays a crucial role in the digestion and absorption of lipids in the small intestine (Ticho et al. 2020). It is a conjugate of cholic acid and taurine and is naturally found in mammals such as bovine bile. Owing to its amphipathic structure, sodium taurocholate can form micelles, which aid in the solubilization of poorly water-soluble, lipophilic compounds, thereby enhancing their bioavailability (Small 1968). In pharmaceutical and biopharmaceutical research, sodium taurocholate is frequently used as a key component in biorelevant dissolution media that simulate intestinal fluids under fasted or fed conditions (Klein 2010). These media are essential for *in vitro* dissolution testing of oral dosage forms, especially for drugs with limited solubility. In recent years, there has been growing interest in exploring alternative, natural sources of sodium taurocholate, such as bovine bile, to reduce dependency on synthetic or commercial-grade materials.

Due to its high sensitivity, specificity, and reproducibility, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) has become one of the most reliable analytical techniques for the separation and quantification of bile acids. However, the complex matrix of bile extract can pose significant analytical challenges, necessitating the development of a robust and validated method to ensure precise quantification.

This study aimed to develop and validate a high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) method for determining sodium taurocholate in bovine bile extract following standard validation parameters, including selectivity, linearity, accuracy, precision, limit of detection (LOD), and limit of quantification (LOQ). A validated analytical method is critical for routine quality control and regulatory compliance in the production and utilization of bovine bile extract.

Figure 1. Chemical structure of sodium taurocholate.

Materials and methods

Materials

All reagents used were of analytical grade, unless specified otherwise. HPLC-grade methanol was purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Potassium dihydrogen phosphate and dipotassium hydrogen phosphate were

purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Taurocholic acid sodium salt (purity 98%) was purchased from Sigma Chemical Co. (St. Louis, MO).

Standard preparation

The standard solution was prepared by dissolving 25 mg of sodium taurocholate in a 25 mL volumetric flask using purified water. Suitable aliquots of the resulting solution were subsequently diluted to prepare standard solutions with different concentrations (10, 20, 30, 40, 60, 80, and 100 µg/mL).

Ethanol extract of bovine bile

Bovine bile was extracted using 96% ethanol at a 1:4 ratio. The ethanol extract was washed three times with *n*-hexane at a 1:1 ratio. The extract was then dried at 40 °C. The concentration of sodium taurocholate was determined using HPLC.

Sample preparation

The sample was prepared by weighing 25 mg of ethanolic bile extract and then transferring it into a 25 mL volumetric flask. Then, 5 mL of purified water was added, and the mixture was sonicated for 5 minutes. The solution was made up to 25 mL with purified water. Subsequently, 500 µL of the solution was added to a 5 mL volumetric flask, and the mixture was made up to 5 mL with purified water. The solution was filtered using a 0.45 µm membrane filter. The concentration of the extract solution was 100 ppm.

High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)

HPLC analysis was performed on a Waters HPLC system (Milford, Massachusetts, USA), equipped with a 1525 binary pump, a 2707 autosampler, and a 2487 UV-Vis detector. The analytical column was Shodex C18-4E (250 × 4.6 mm, 5 µm, Showa Denko, Japan). A sample injection volume of 50 µL was used in all experiments. The mobile phase containing a mixture of 25 mM KH₂PO₄/K₂HPO₄ (pH 5.45) and methanol (22:78, v/v) was pumped through the column at a flow rate of 0.7 mL/min, and the quantification was achieved at 210 nm using a UV-Vis detector. The mobile phase was filtered through a 0.22 µm membrane filter and degassed prior to HPLC analysis.

Method validation

Specificity

The analysis was performed by testing the solvent, a 100 µg/mL sodium taurocholate standard, and the bovine bile extract sample. Specificity was assessed by the absence of interfering peaks around the retention time of sodium taurocholate.

Linearity

The test was conducted by analyzing a series of sodium taurocholate standard solutions at seven different concentrations. The concentration range of the calibration curve was established around the *in vivo* concentration of sodium taurocholate in bovine bile (determined during the trial). The series was prepared by diluting a 1,000 µg/mL sodium taurocholate stock solution with distilled water to obtain standard solutions at 10, 20, 30, 40, 60, 80, and 100 µg/mL. A calibration curve was constructed by plotting the concentration of the sodium taurocholate standards against the area under the curve obtained from HPLC analysis, and the regression line was calculated using the equation $y = mx + c$, where y is the peak area, x is the concentration of drug, m is the slope, and c is the intercept.

Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ)

The LOD and LOQ were calculated from the data obtained in the linearity test using Equations (1) and (2):

$$\text{Limit of detection(LOD)} = 3.3 \times S_{y/x}/S \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Limit of quantification(LOQ)} = 10 \times S_{y/x}/S \quad (2)$$

In both equations, $S_{y/x}$ represents the standard deviation of the residuals, and S is the slope obtained from the sodium taurocholate calibration curve.

Accuracy

Accuracy testing was performed using the standard addition method by spiking the bovine bile extract sample. The spiked samples were prepared by pipetting extract samples with a specific concentration of the sodium taurocholate standard at 80%, 100%, and 120% of the theoretical concentration (28 µg/mL, 35 µg/mL, and 48 µg/mL, respectively) into microtubes. The mixtures were homogenized and then analyzed by HPLC. Three replicates were prepared for each concentration. The percentage recovery for each result was calculated by comparing the corrected concentration obtained with the theoretical concentration.

Precision

The precision of the assay was evaluated in terms of both repeatability and reproducibility. Precision refers to the consistency of test results when the method is applied repeatedly to multiple samples under the same conditions. It was assessed through intra-day and inter-day repeatability by analyzing replicate injections, and the results were expressed as the relative standard deviation (RSD%). The RSD% was calculated using the formula:

$$\%RSD = \frac{\text{Standard deviation of recovered concentration}}{\text{Mean recovered concentration}} \times 100\%$$

In this method development and validation study, precision was assessed by performing six replicate analyses at 35 µg/mL of the standard sodium taurocholate solution using the proposed method.

Result

Method development

The method development was initiated by optimizing chromatographic conditions to achieve suitable retention time and peak resolution for sodium taurocholate (NaTC). A reversed-phase C18 column was selected due to its compatibility with bile salt compounds. Initially, a mobile phase consisting of 25 mM phosphate buffer (pH 5.45) and methanol (25:75, v/v) at a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min was evaluated. The mobile phase consisting of 25 mM phosphate buffer (pH 5.45) and methanol (22:78, v/v) in isocratic mode provided optimal separation at a flow rate of 0.7 mL/min, minimized tailing, and provided better resolution. The maximum wavelength of sodium taurocholate was determined by scanning the wavelength range of 200–210 nm using a UV spectrophotometer (Lin et al. 2020). Detection was carried out at 210 nm, where sodium taurocholate exhibited maximum absorbance. The retention time for sodium taurocholate was found to be approximately 8.5 minutes. The chromatogram of the working standard sodium taurocholate solution is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Chromatogram of sodium taurocholate standard.

Suitability system

To evaluate system suitability, six injections of the standard solution at 60 µg/mL were performed. All essential parameters consistently met the specified acceptance criteria across all testing days. Key chromatographic parameters were calculated, including tailing factor, theoretical plate count, and capacity factor (k'). The results are presented in Table 1. Tailing factor, theoretical plate count, and capacity factor (k') were automatically calculated by the HPLC software.

Specificity

Specificity refers to the ability of an analytical method to unequivocally assess the analyte in the presence of other components that may be expected to be present, such as impurities, degradation products, and matrix components (ICH 2023).

Table 1. System suitability data for sodium taurocholate.

Number of injections	Retention time (min)	Area
1	8.747	326073
2	8.731	330482
3	8.717	328911
4	8.696	329742
5	8.681	329351
6	8.676	333591
Mean	8.71	329691.67
SD	0.03	2435.25
%RSD	0.33	0.74
Tailing factor		1.42
Plate count		9220
k'		16.4

The specificity test was performed by analyzing purified water as a solvent (blank), a sodium taurocholate standard solution, and the sample solution. The chromatograms obtained in the selectivity test are shown in Fig. 3. No interfering peaks were observed at the retention time of sodium taurocholate in the blank and sample chromatograms, indicating that the developed method is specific for the determination of sodium taurocholate (ICH 2023).

Figure 3. Overlay of chromatogram solvent, sodium taurocholate (NaTC) standard solution, and sample extract.

Linearity

Linearity of an analytical method refers to its ability, within a given range, to produce test results that are directly proportional to the concentration (amount) of analyte in the sample (ICH 2023). The linearity test was performed by analyzing a series of sodium taurocholate standard solutions with concentrations ranging from 10 to 100 µg/mL. The calibration curve was obtained by plotting the sodium taurocholate concentration against the corresponding peak area (response), as presented in Fig. 4. The resulting calibration curve equation was $y = 5773.92x - 12429.93$, with a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.9997. These results indicate that the analytical method is linear within the range of 10–100 µg/mL (ICH 2023).

Figure 4. Calibration curve of sodium taurocholate.

Limit of detection and limit of quantification

Sodium taurocholate standard solutions at concentrations of 10, 20, 30, 40, 60, 80, and 100 µg/mL were prepared by diluting the stock solution using purified water. The LOD and LOQ for sodium taurocholate under the established chromatographic conditions were determined based on signal-to-noise ratios of 3:1 and 10:1, respectively, by injecting diluted solutions of known concentrations. The LOD and LOQ values for sodium taurocholate were determined to be 2.83 µg/mL and 8.57 µg/mL, respectively.

Precision

Precision is a measure that indicates the degree of agreement (or spread) among a series of measurements obtained from a homogeneous sample under specified conditions (ICH 2023). Precision testing was conducted through intra-day precision, which reflects repeatability, and inter-day precision, which reflects reproducibility across two different days. The results of the precision test are shown in Table 2. The intra-day precision test yielded an RSD% of 0.6%, while the inter-day precision test produced RSD% values of 0.6%, 0.87%, and 0.71%. The combined data from the inter-day precision test resulted in an RSD% of 1.28%. Therefore, the precision of the method for determining sodium taurocholate content in the extract meets the acceptance criteria, with an RSD% ≤ 5.0% (Latimer 2023a).

Table 2. Precision data evaluated through intra-day and inter-day studies.

Replication number	Day 1	Day 2	
	Area	Area	Area
1	190146	185468.67	188331
2	188280	183070.67	184735
3	191645	185539.67	185300
4	189440	183155.67	186550
5	189321	185462.67	187418
6	189284	187239.67	186421
Average	189686.00	184989.50	186459.17
SD	1129.73	1604.01	1322.82
RSD%	0.60	0.87	0.71
RSD% ($n = 18$)		1.28	

Accuracy

Accuracy is a measure that indicates the degree of closeness between the analytical result and the actual concentration of the analyte. Accuracy is expressed as the percentage of analyte recovery from a spiked sample (ICH 2023). The accuracy test was carried out using spiked samples, in which bovine bile ethanol extract was spiked with sodium taurocholate standard at 80%, 100%, and 120% of the theoretical concentration. The results of the accuracy test are shown in Table 3. The average percentage recovery in this test ranged from 100.01% to 100.93%. Since the acceptable recovery range for accuracy is 95.0% to 105.0% (BPOM 2025), the accuracy of the analytical method used for determining sodium taurocholate content in the extract meets the required criteria.

Table 3. Accuracy data evaluated through intra-day and inter-day studies.

Conc. ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Intra-day ($n = 3$)		Inter-day ($n = 3$)	
	Mean recovery% \pm SD ($n = 3$)	RSD%	Mean recovery% \pm SD ($n = 3$)	RSD%
28	100.17 \pm 2.81	2.80	100.01 \pm 0.85	0.85
35	100.79 \pm 0.40	0.40	100.52 \pm 0.26	0.26
42	101.85 \pm 0.98	0.96	100.93 \pm 1.84	1.84

Determination of sodium taurocholate in ethanol extract of bovine bile

The bovine bile used as raw material was obtained from a slaughterhouse in Bandung, Indonesia. The sodium taurocholate content in the extract obtained from the trial extraction of bovine bile was determined, and the result showed a concentration of 18.93%.

Discussion

The primary objective of developing the chromatographic method was to determine the concentration of sodium taurocholate in an extract with a complex matrix. Through the developed chromatographic method, sodium taurocholate can be separated from interfering matrix components present in the extract. Reversed-phase chromatography was chosen for the analysis of sodium taurocholate. In this method, the stationary phase is nonpolar, while the mobile phase is polar. Sodium taurocholate, being a highly polar compound, was well suited for separation using reversed-phase chromatography, where a nonpolar stationary phase and a polar mobile phase system enable polar analytes to elute earlier.

The method development in this study was based on a previously reported HPLC method for bile acid analysis, which utilized a reversed-phase C18 column and a phosphate buffer-methanol mobile phase system (Lin et al. 2000). However, several modifications were introduced to improve the applicability of the method for sodium taurocholate determination in a complex extract matrix. In this study, the optimized mobile phase composition and chromatographic conditions resulted in improved peak symmetry, reduced tailing, and adequate resolution from matrix interferences. In addition, the developed

method demonstrated a consistent retention time and good reproducibility, indicating its suitability for routine analysis.

Compared to the reference method, which was primarily designed for the simultaneous determination of multiple bile acids in relatively simpler biological matrices, the present method offers better selectivity for sodium taurocholate in a more complex extract system while maintaining reliable chromatographic performance.

The method demonstrated excellent linearity over the tested concentration range, with a correlation coefficient (r) greater than 0.999. The LOD and LOQ were sufficiently low to allow detection of sodium taurocholate even at trace levels in the extract. Precision and accuracy values complied with acceptance criteria based on International Council for Harmonization (ICH) guidelines, confirming the method's reliability for routine analysis.

Furthermore, the recovery studies showed minimal matrix effect, indicating the method's robustness despite the biological complexity of the bovine bile extract. This finding highlights the effectiveness of the chromatographic separation in isolating sodium taurocholate from interfering substances.

In summary, the validated RP-HPLC method provides a simple, sensitive, and reproducible approach for quantifying sodium taurocholate in complex biological matrices. This method can be applied to the quality control of natural bile-based products or as part of research involving bile salt-based dissolution media.

Conclusion

The analytical method for determining the sodium taurocholate content in ethanolic bovine bile extract has been successfully developed and validated. All tested validation parameters met the required criteria. Therefore, this analytical method can be used for the routine determination of sodium taurocholate content in ethanolic bovine bile extract.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.